

**Northumbria
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NEWCASTLE

Characterisation of Print Path Deviation in 3D Printed Continuous Carbon Fibre Composites

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The Opportunity

Images: Markforged

The Challenge

Tao et al., 2021

The Challenge

Our Solution

Characterise & Understand

Regenerate & Model

Design & Create

3D Printer Setup

Geetech A20T

3-in-1 extruder

modified CCF extruder

Printing

carbon fibre-nylon filament
printed at 5 mm/s

Straight paths

Angled corners (45°, 90° and 135°)

Curved paths (2, 4, 6 and 8mm radius)

Image Processing

Characterisation

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \delta_i^2}{N}}$$

Root mean squared deviation (RMSD)

Mean Deviation from ideal	-0.009 mm
RMSD	0.062 mm

Results – 45°

Results – 90°

Results – 135°

Results – Angled Corners

Results – Curves

Results – Curves

Key Advancement

- Statistical characterisation of fibre position
- Range of geometric features

Implications & Future Development

Fibre Cross-section

Regenerate & Model

Optimise structures

Benchmarking & Maintenance

